

IDEA: Integrating Diversity in Evaluation and Assessment of Researchers

This project has received funding from the CoARA Boost Programme, funded by the European Commission

IDEA – workshop 1 results

Date: 05-03-2025

Participants: 8 participants in this workshop representing 5 different faculties at the VU, as well as the central policy level (including 1 responder who met the researchers to give input before the workshop); 2 of these were members of the diversity office and 6 were representatives of central or faculty Recognition and Rewards policies

Results

The status quo regarding the implementation of Recognition and Rewards at the faculties

- Some faculties are further ahead with regard to developing an implementation plan for Recognition and Rewards. Some have used extensive co-creative approaches with researchers across ranks to developing theirs. Some of the policies are already up on the VU website, while others are not yet.
- It would be beneficial to do analysis of the existing implementation plans with the perspective of diversity in mind. A similar analysis has been done by the library focusing on open Science.
- Implementation plans across faculties are developed in such a way, that it is up to departments to concretely apply the Recognition and Rewards policies to the work floor.
- Kinds of outputs coming from IDEA that would be useful for departments:
 - Addressing concrete questions (e.g. compensation for young parents that go for leave)
 - Contributions/input towards workshops, trainings, coaching, mentorship plans
 - A toolkit collecting all existing practices, options and knowledge

General concerns at the university regarding Recognition and Rewards & Diversity

- The VU has a diverse student population so it is attractive for diverse students, but it is not attractive for researchers, especially those with less resourcefulness (e.g. caregivers, those from lower and middle-class backgrounds). This is becoming worse with pending budget cuts.
- There is a slow change that is coming regarding the balance of valuing teaching and researcher. Previously research was mostly prioritized also over teaching, and while this is still the extent to a large extent, there are developments that are shifting the balance a bit. For instance, the VU is introducing promotion tracks based on teaching profiles. However, even with these developments, teaching will likely remain to be undervalued and undercompensated, since the VU as a university has research as its distinguishing factor.
- There is still little focus on valuing collaboration in researcher evaluations. Team Science needs to be more recognized.
- Little attention has been paid within Recognition and Rewards on the fact that ambiguous promotion criteria are a barrier for diversity. The shift away from quantitative metrics to narrative CVs might worsen existing problems for diversity and equity. Therefore, there is a need for reflection on how to balance quantitative and qualitative indicators in researcher evaluations. Furthermore, assessors need to themselves be

aware of the need to look not only at what candidates have achieved, but also the context of the person at hand.

- There are concerns that the changes taking place with Recognition and Rewards will limit researchers with regard to mobility and interdisciplinarity (i.e. if different requirements are pursued in different faculties, countries, and institutions.)
- The change with Recognition and Reward target assistant to full professors, but not PhDs and early career researchers for whom much ambiguity still remains. However, there are now discussions about whether, and if so how, to implement Recognition and Rewards for this target group. Some important considerations include: 1) PhD theses are evaluated by external assessors, 2) the PhD is recognized as an academic degree, 3) transparency is important on what is evaluated also between universities, 4) some faculties are taking steps to change things. For instance, for Religion and Theology, a positionality chapter is now a requirement for the PhD.
- There is unease among some about the obligation to choose one specific career path. In some faculties, everyone chooses the research path as the education path seems more risky and there remains a struggle to balance research and teaching. In the past, it was thought that a general profile is a 'safer' option. These general profiles will now only be options in some faculties (depending on dean's preferences) at the VU.

What kind of output could be helpful for R&R implementation with diversity in mind?

- Action plan
- Practical toolbox aimed at departments.
- Reflection tool that includes positionality and collaboration tool to support team science.
- Analysis of implementation plans from the perspective of diversity
- Input to Chief Diversity Officer to relay to rector before July for institutional diversity policies.